

Public–Private Organisation Differentials in Relationship of Leadership Styles, Job Satisfaction and Organisational Commitment in Nigeria

¹.KENKU, Akeem A. (PhD), ².OGUNKUADE, Idowu M. (PhD)

¹Department of Psychology, Faculty of Social Sciences, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria.

²Department of Administration, Nigerian Copyright Commission, Headquarters, Abuja, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT: *This study examined the relationship of public and private organisations differential in leadership styles and job satisfaction on organizational commitment in Nigeria. A survey of four hundred and fifty-seven (457) employees of private and public sector organisations was undertaken, using a structured self-report questionnaire which had four sections. One hundred and eighty-four 184(40.3%) of the respondents were from private organizations and two hundred and seventy-three 273 (59.7%) were from public organizations. The age of the respondents ranged from 22 to 54years with a mean age of 35.77years and standard deviation of 12.76 years. There were 259 (56.7%) males and females 198(43.3%). Two (2) hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis (PPMC) and t-test for independence measure. There results demonstrated that there were significant positive relationships between transformational leadership style [$r = .14$], transactional leadership style [$r = .10$], job satisfaction [$r = .42$], and organizational commitment. Other result of the study explains, thattype of organization significantly influence organizational commitment. $t [455] = 4.08, P < .05$. The study concluded that, there is a significant positive relationship of leadership styles, job satisfaction, and organisational commitment in Nigerian organization, and suggestthe need to embrace transformational leadership and transactional leadership styles in different situations in Nigeria in a bid to increasing organizational commitment, effectiveness, and performance..*

Keywords: *organisational commitment, job satisfaction, leadership styles, organization types, relationship.*

I. Introduction

In the twenty-first century, public and private organizations world over particularly in Nigeria are established primarily to accomplish predetermined set goals and objectives. In achieving these goals and objectives, the role of the human elements (employees) cannot be overemphasized (Gberevbie, 2017; Mottoh, 2015). This is simply because organizations, irrespective of other resources (financial, land, technological) at their disposal, cannot achieve anything meaningful in terms of attaining its set goals, without putting into consideration workers commitment and other resources (Gberevbie, Joshua, Excellence-Oluye, & Oyeyemi, 2017; Jain & Duggal, 2015).

However, organisational commitment is one of job-related attitudes that have been well researched in the field of industrial and organisational psychology and other human resource management and practitioners and its significance has been documented in the literatures. This job-related attitude is an important organizational subject because high levels of commitment lead to several favourable organizational outcomes (Parvin, Kabir&Nurul, 2011; Folorunso, Adewale & Abodunde, 2014). The literature suggests that individuals become

committed to organizations for a variety of reasons, including an affective attachment to the values of the organization, a realization of the costs involved with leaving the organization, and a sense of obligation to the organization (Meyer & Allen, 1997). According to Khan, Razi, Ali and Asghar (2011), committed employees benefit their organizations in many ways. They will put forth extra efforts in fulfilling their job, engage in extra-role behaviour, and help organization function smoothly. Past studies indicate that organizational commitment is negatively related to turnover intentions (Cooper-Hakim & Viswesvaran, 2005), absenteeism (Farrell & Stamm, 1988), and positively related to satisfaction, performance (Chen & Francesco, 2003), and motivation of employees (Mathieu & Zajac, 1990).

To date, many different definitions for this concept have been suggested (Buciuniene & Skudiene, 2008), and the reason for this is that it has a multi-dimensional structure that includes the attitude and behavioral components of commitment to work (Meyer, Allen, & Smith, 1993). Organizational commitment was defined as the strength of an employee's identification with the organization (Porter, Steers, Mowday, & Boulian, 1974). According to this definition, organizational commitment consists of three components: (1) having absolute belief in the objectives and values of the organization, (2) making all efforts necessary for the benefit of the organization and (3) having a strong desire to continue with that organization. It is also emphasized that it is a process.

Given this, there are several job-related factors that are considered vital to organizational commitment. According to Morakinyo (2010), who maintained that organizational commitment is affected by such factors as personal characteristics; work experience; leadership-motivation; structural factors and personnel policies. This study single out the role of leadership styles, job satisfaction as less explored antecedents of organisational commitment in the Nigerian organizations. Effective leadership styles have been prescribed for improving organizational productivity through organizational commitment. Leadership and its effectiveness is primary focus for profit organization to achieve the organizational goals and to create organization commitment in their employees, for their organizations. This leadership is demonstrated in having vision and being able to transform that vision into action by influencing others to perform at higher levels and promoting the importance of organizational and interpersonal citizenship behaviors (Fashola, Adeyemi & Olowe, 2013). Abdul, Ausnain and Munawar (2012) have associated both transformational and transactional leadership styles to organizational commitment. It is therefore, an imperative to ascertain the contributions of transactional and transformational leadership styles to organizational commitment in the present study.

Also, job satisfaction is of interest in relation to organisational commitment in the present study, as job satisfaction is a central component of most approaches to understanding organisational outcomes. It was observed that for any organisation to neglect its significance, is similar to an accountant submitting an annual report without a profit-and-loss statement (Bullock, 1994). As a concept, job satisfaction has been broadly studied in literature because many experts, managers as well as researchers, believe that job satisfaction influences a variety of organisational behaviours and outcomes such as productivity, employee turnover, organisational commitment, employee retention, prosociality and extra-role behaviours (Spector, 1997). Job satisfaction is the pleasant and positive emotional status after the evaluation of the job or work experience (Hackman & Oldham, 1976). It has been classified into three main classes: intrinsic, extrinsic and overall job satisfaction (Weiss, Dawis, England, & Lofquist, 1967). An employee is intrinsically satisfied if he/she receives no apparent reward except the activity itself, while an employee is extrinsically satisfied if he/she receives monetary compensation or other material rewards to modify his/her behaviour (Rose, 2001). Overall job satisfaction is a combination of both intrinsic and extrinsic job satisfaction. The generic understanding of job satisfaction holds that it is a collection of feelings and beliefs that a person has about his job, which may derive from an aspect of satisfaction or as an overall facet of the job (George and Jones, 1999; Spector, 2006). Basically, employee satisfaction is a measure of how happy workers are with their job and working environment (Osemeke, 2016).

Previous and more recent studies show that high levels of organizational commitment is a required catalyst to decrease turnover, increase productivity, performance, retention and job satisfaction. As a result, several researchers have increasingly tried to identify antecedents that determine employee organizational commitment. This is because for researchers to alter commitment, they have to understand its antecedents. Antecedents of organisational commitment such as: monetary rewards (Omolayo and Owolabi, 2007), psychological and demography factors (Salami, 2008), structure (Ardrey et al., 2001), human resources practice, job satisfaction, leadership behavior, and extra role-behaviour (Gbadamosi, 2003) have been demonstrated in the cross-sectional studies to influence organizational commitment. Nevertheless, their evidences have been mixed about organizational commitment especially for the impact of job satisfaction.

II. Statement of the Problem

Nigeria is blessed with abundant human and material resources which make her the giant of Africa. Despite, the fact of her giant position in the community of nations particularly in Africa, the service organisations has not been contributing significantly to the Nigerian economy. In line with this opinion, Awoseyin (2007) observe that the Nigerian public and private sector organisations are faced with quantum of problems. Among them are poor services and unethical behaviours by employees' in the service organisations. Consequently, many reputable organisations in Nigeria, have moribund while surviving ones are still performing below an expected standard. This may be as a result of poor management styles, low job satisfaction, and lack of organizational commitment among the employees, which might have created negative job attitudes. In this direction, organizational commitment has been examined in both public and private organisations in both developed and developing countries. However, there is dearth of studies, especially in Nigeria, that addresses the association of leadership styles, employee satisfaction, and organizational commitment in Nigerian Service Organisations. It is in the light of this, the study intends to fill the gap in knowledge by focusing on the public-private organisations differential in relationship of leadership styles, job satisfaction and organisational commitment in the selected organisations in Abuja, Nigeria.

III. Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study is to assess the public-private organisation differentials in relationship of leadership styles, job satisfaction and Organisational Commitment in Nigeria. While, the specific objectives include the followings:

1. To evaluate the relationship between leadership styles, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment in Nigeria.
2. To examine the comparison of employees commitment in public and private sector organizations on organizational commitment.

Research Questions

- i. To what extent is leadership styles and job satisfaction significantly associate with organizational commitment in Nigeria?
- ii. What is the significant comparison of employees' commitment in public and private sector organizations on organizational commitment?

IV. Literature review

Available studies have compared employees' commitment of service organisations particularly private and public sectors. Previous study like Chovwen and Ogunsakin (2013) demonstrated that employees in private sector exhibits more work performance behaviour in their organisation than public servants. High commitment behaviour was assumed to be prevalent in the private sector due to the exceptional differences in organizational climate and human resource management. They deplored the common practice of non-chalant attitudes and lack of innovative human resource management in government ministries and parastatals. Goulet and Frank (2002) demonstrated that there were significant differences in the job commitment of employees in public, non-profit,

and for profit as the lowest levels of organisational commitment were displayed among the civil servants. These differences were linked to differences in remuneration and benefits accruing to the employees. Njoku, Ebeh, & Mbaeri, (2017) also reported that there was a significant difference in employees' organizational commitment due to personality traits. In conclusion, Kipkebut, (2010) found that human resource practices was significant determinants of differences between a public and private Universities workers in Kenya in terms of normative and continuance commitment.

In terms of the relationship between job satisfaction and organisational commitment, a number of previous researchers have also reported mixed findings on the two concepts (job satisfaction and organizational commitment). For instance, A study conducted by Dirani and Kuchinke (2011) produced results indicating a strong correlation between job satisfaction and job commitment and that satisfaction was a reliable predictor of commitment. According to the study conducted by Gunlu and Aksarayli, (2010) on Job satisfaction and Organizational commitment of hotel managers in Turkey, the findings indicate that extrinsic, intrinsic, and general job satisfaction have a significant effect on commitment. Loui (1995) examined the relationship between job satisfaction and organizational commitment among 109 workers and reported that there are positive relationship between organizational commitment and job satisfaction. A study by Rajendran and Raduan (2005) showed the same result that is job satisfaction has a positive influence on affective and normative commitment. Also, Adnan and Muhammad (2010) conducted a study to find out the antecedents of Job satisfaction in telecom sector and result established a positive relationship between job satisfaction and commitment.

In addition, Goulet and Frank (2002) in a study of employees from three different sectors (public, non-profit, and for profit), supported the view that the lowest levels of organisational commitment are exhibited in the public sector. Further to the above (Jurkiewicz et al., 1998) found that respondents from two large private firms placed a higher value on the opportunity to be useful to society than did respondents from a variety of local government agencies in a metropolitan area. Gabris and Sim (1995) found that public sector employees were not different from private sector employees in preference. For monetary rewards or for opportunities to help others, which implies that there levels of commitment is not differs (Perry and Porter, 1982).

Research Hypotheses

- i. There will be a significant positive relationship between leadership styles, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment in Nigeria
- ii. There will be a significant difference between private and public employees based on Organizational Commitment.

V. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research approach adopted in this study is a cross-sectional survey research design method. It involves using of standardized and structured questionnaire in collecting data from the respondents. Also, this is considered appropriate due to the researchers' inability to directly manipulate the variables of the study.

Participants

A total of four hundred and fifty-seven (457) workers participated in this study and were employees selected from private and public service organizations in Nigeria. Their socio-demographic characteristics revealed that 259 males (56.7%), 198 females (43.3%). The employees job tenure ranged from 1-35 years with a mean tenure of 14.36 years (SD= 5.17). As regards marital status, 124(27.1%) were single, 330(72.2%) were married and 3(0.7%) were divorced. For years of experience, 124(27.1%) had 1-4 years of experience, 111(24.3%) had 5-9 years of experience, 112(24.5%) had 10-14 years of experience, 34(7.4%) had 15-19 years of experience and 76(16.6%) had 20 years. Based on organization type 184(40.3%) were in private organization while 273(59.7%) were in public organization. Finally, on educational qualification, 118 (25.8%) acquired diploma certificate,

177(38.7%) possessed degree certificate, 57(12.5%) acquired professional certificate, 64(14%) were masters holder, 14(3.1%) bagged PhD certificate and 27(5.9%) had other certificates.

Setting

This study was carried out among some selected service private and public organisations located in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria. The rationale for using this setting is because the organisations are accessible to the researchers.

Research Instruments

The main instrument used for this study was a structured questionnaires booklet which was divided into four sections: **The socio-demographic variables.**

This section comprises of socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents used in the study. These variables includes: age, gender, education qualification, marital status and year of experience/tenure.

Organisational commitment was measured using the organisational commitment questionnaire (OCQ), developed by Mowday, Steers and Porter (1979). OCQ contains 15 items that measure an employee's level of commitment to his/her organisation. The respondents indicate the extent to which each item reflect their commitment to their organisation on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree. Sample items include: I feel very little loyalty to this organisation; I am proud to tell others that I am part of this organisation; I really care about the fate of this organisation; deciding to work for this organisation was a definite mistake on my part. The negatively phrased items (3, 7, 9, 11, 12, and 15) are reverse scored. Higher scores indicate more commitment to the organisation. The original authors reported a Cronbach's alpha of .91 and .89 for professional and clerical samples

respectively. OCQ has been used in several studies in Nigeria with reliability coefficient (Cronbach's alpha) of .83 (Tella, Ayeni & Popoola, 2007). An internal consistency reliability (Cronbach's alpha) of .76 and split-half reliability coefficient of .64 was obtained in the present study.

Job satisfaction was assessed with the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ), developed by Weiss, Dawis, England and Lofquist (1967). MSQ has 20 items which are scored on a 5-point Likert scale of very satisfied (1) to very dissatisfied (5). Respondents are requested to indicate the extent of their satisfaction or dissatisfaction with some job-related factors e.g. variety, compensation, recognition, working conditions, supervision, etc. Sample items include; on my present job, this is how I feel about...: (1) Being able to keep busy all the time, (5) the way my boss handles his/her workers, (17) the working conditions, (20) the feeling of accomplishment I get from the job. Weiss et al (1967) reported test-retest reliabilities coefficients of .89 at one-week interval and .70 at one-year interval. Mogaji (1996) obtained a 10-week test-retest reliability coefficient of .71 in a Nigerian sample. A high internal consistency reliability coefficient (Cronbach's alpha) of .85 and moderate split-half reliability of .78 were obtained in the current study.

The two leadership styles was measured with Multi-Factor Leadership Questionnaires (MLQ) developed by Avolio and Bass (1990) on the 5 point Likert format, ranging from "1-not at all to 5-frequently". The questionnaires comprised of 27 items in all, 18 questions to measures the transformational leadership style and the rest 9 questions measures the transactional leadership with a slight change in the arrangement. A sample items on the scale for transformational leadership are: "I let others work in the manner that they want", "I get things done", and "I ensure poor performance get corrected". Sample items for transactional leadership style are: "I keep track of all mistakes", and I provide recognition/rewards when others reach their goals". The reliability coefficient for transformational leadership style was found to be 0.83 and for transactional leadership style it was 0.65.

Procedure

Prior to questionnaires distribution/administration, consultations were held with the head of human resources units and departments of each of the organisations to describe the study and motive of the research study. After the researchers have confidently sought for participants consent to participate in the study, they were informed that they should rate the items on the instrument that best describes their opinions on each instrument/questionnaire, and research participants were guaranteed absolute confidentiality of the information given which was used solely for the purpose of which the study aims to achieve. The data collection for the study lasted for about 6 weeks. Six hundred (600) questionnaires were administered; five hundred and fifty (550) was recovered. Ninety-three (93) copies of the returned questionnaires were discarded due to improper completion, leaving a total of four hundred and fifty-seven (457) copies that were used for data analysis, which gave a response rate of 76.2%.

Method of Data analysis

Following the design of the study and the nature of scale, the statistical techniques that were used include means, standard deviations, Pearson Product Moment Correlation test, and t-test for independent sample measure.

VI. Results

Hypothesis one which states that there will be relationship between leadership styles, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment in Nigeria was tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation test and the summary of result presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis showing the relationship between Transformational leadership style, Transactional leadership style, Job satisfaction, and Organizational Commitment

Variables	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4
1. Organizational commitment	59.33	8.90	-			
2. Transformational leadership style	69.49	10.41	.14**	-		
3. Transactional leadership style	32.22	5.64	.10*	.58**	-	
4. Job satisfaction	72.59	10.70	.42**	.37**		-

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 1 reveals that there was significant positive relationship between transformational leadership style ($r = .14, p < .01$), transactional leadership style ($r = .10, p < .05$), job satisfaction ($r = .42, p < .01$), and organizational commitment indicating that increase in transformational leadership style, transactional leadership style, and job satisfaction, significantly relate to increase in organizational commitment. With this result, the hypothesis was confirmed and accepted.

Hypothesis two states that there will be a significant difference between employees in private and public sector organizations on organizational commitment were tested using the t-test for independence and the result presented in **Table 2**.

Table 2: Summary t-test for independence table showing difference between private and public employees' based on Organizational Commitment.

D.V	Organization	N	Mean	S.D	df	t	P
Organizational commitment	Private	184	61.36	9.14	455	4.08	<0.05
	Public	273	57.96	8.49			

The result above shows that employees in private organization(M=61.36, S.D= 9.14) significantly reported higher scores on organizational commitment compare to employees in public organization(M=57.96, S.D =8.49). By this result, employees in private organization significantly reported more organizational commitment ($t(455) = 4.08, p < .01$) than employees in public organization. This implies that type of organization significantly influence organizational commitment. The result confirmed the second hypothesis that there will be significant difference between private and public employees based on organisational commitment.

VII. Discussions

The crux of the study was to assess organization comparison in relationship between leadership styles, job satisfaction, and organisational commitment in Nigeria. Two hypotheses were tested based on the nature of data collected. The first hypothesis stated that there will be significant relationship between leadership styles, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment in Nigeria was confirmed by the result. The result demonstrates the expected effect of leadership styles and job satisfaction have on organizational commitment was significant. This finding supported the finding of Jaskyte, 2004; Avolio and Bass, 1994; and Elloy, 2005 that employees' perceptions of leadership behavior and job-related factors were important predictor of organizational commitment, which revealed that a combination of leadership styles (transformational and transactional), and job satisfaction, seems not to only influence commitment, but also to determine it.

With regard to the second hypothesis which states that employees in private sector organizations will report more organizational commitment than their counterpart in the public sector organizations was supported. The probable explanation for this is that employee commitment differs across different sectors of the economy, as such, public sector jobs differs from jobs available in the private sector in such terms as salaries, benefits, task types, and performance criteria. As a result, the result corroborates the assertion of Akintayo, 2008; Bar-on and Parker, 2000; and Chovwen and Ogunsakin, 2013, that positive job outcome is assumed to be prevalent in the private sector because of the inherent differences in terms of climate, policies and practices. Whereas, in the public sector, especially government ministries and parastatals problems of nonchalant attitude and reluctance in taking initiatives are prevalent.

VIII. Conclusion

The objective of the research work is to examine the organization comparison in relationship between leadership styles, job satisfaction, and organisational commitment in Nigeria. Cross-section survey research design was used to investigate the relationship between these variables. The findings have indicated that transformational, transactional leadership styles, job satisfaction, were able to predict organisational commitment. In this sense, this study represents the theoretical and empirical research regarding leadership styles, job satisfaction and organizational commitment in the public and private sectors. It is believed that this study have added value to the literatures on supervisors, managers, leadership styles and organizational commitment, particularly in the Nigerian settings, since there were limited literatures done on similar setting. On this note, the current study concluded that leadership styles and employees' job-related phenomena were significant in influencing expression of employees' organizational commitment in both public and private organizations in Nigeria.

Limitations of the study/Suggestions for further research

The researchers encountered various limitations during the course of conducting the study, these limitations include – the enormous difficulty in distributing and collecting data from a busy group of private sectors' employees. This made the size of the sample relatively small compared to the population of the civil servants in Nigeria. Therefore, this limits generalising the results of the study to the whole organisations in Nigeria. Financial constraints and time frame also limited the scope that the study would have covered. Another limitation is that the researchers measured the data for all variables using self-reporting scales. It was impossible to verify the accuracy and honesty of the workers' self-reported data. However, the aforementioned limitations did not have significant effect whatsoever on the objectivity of the findings of the study.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the study, the following recommendations are offered for practical applications: Managers should apply the mix of both transformational and transactional styles of leadership, but with due consideration to the situation and nature of work assigned. Also, this study should be replicated using same type of organisations but different commitment measures. Since the limitation of the study therefore relied on only organisation located in Abuja. Larger domain of study would certainly be needed to throw more light on the studied variables.

References

- Abdul Q.C, Ausnain. J and Munawar, .S (2012). The impact of transformational and transactional leadership styles on the motivation of employees in Pakistan. *Pakistan Economic and Social Review*. 50 (2), 223-231.
- Adnan, R. and Muhammad, R. (2010). Antecedents of job satisfaction: A study of telecom sector. *Perspectives of Innovation in Economics and Business*, 4, (1), 66-73
- Akintayo, D.I. (2008). Work-family role conflict and organisational commitment among industrial workers in Nigeria. *Journal of Psychology and Counseling*, 2 (1), 1-8.
- Ardrey IV, W. J., Pecotich, A. J. & Ungar, E. (2001). Structure, commitment and strategic action for Asian transitional nations' financial systems in crisis. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 19(1):18-37
- Avolio, B. J., & Bass, B. M. (1990). *Transformational leadership, charisma, and beyond. Emerging leadership vistas*. Lexington, MA: Lexington Books.
- Awoseyin, L (2007): "Professional ethics in hospitality and tourism", *African Hospitality and Tourism*, 11 (3), 18-22.
- Bar-on, R. & Parker, J.D. (2000). *The handbook of emotional intelligence: theory of development, assessment and application at home, school and workplace*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Bass, B. M., & Avolio, B. J. (1994). *Improving organizational effectiveness through transformational leadership*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage
- Bučūnienė, I & Škudienė, V. (2008) Impact of Leadership Styles on Employees' Organizational Commitment in Lithuanian Manufacturing Companies. *South East European Journal of Economics and Business* 3 (2), 57-66.
- Bullock, M. (1994). Research to optimize human performance. *Australian Journal Physiotherapy* 40, 5-17
- Chowwen, C., & Ogunsakin, A. (2013). Determinants of organisational citizenship behaviour among employees of public and private organisations. *An International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Ethiopia*, 7 (2), 161-174.
- Cooper-Hakim, A., & Viswesvaran, C. (2005). The construct of work commitment: testing a integrative framework. *Psychological Bulletin*, 131, 241-259.
- Diran, K. M. and Kuchinke, K. P. (2011) 'Testing the correlations and investigating the effects of Demographic variables in the Lebanese banking sector', *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 22 (5), 1180 – 1202
- Elloy, D.F. (2005). The influence of super-leader behaviours on organizational commitment, job satisfaction and organizational self-esteem in a self-managed work team. *Leadership and Organisational Development Journal*, 26 (2), 120-127.
- Farrell, D & Stamm, C.L. (1988). Meta-Analysis of the Correlates of Employee Absence. *Human Relations* 41(3) 211-227.
- Fasola, O.A., Adeyemi, M.A., & Olowe, F.T. (2013). Exploring the relationship between transformational, transactional leadership style and organisational commitment among Nigerian Banks Employees. *International Journal of Academic Research in Economics and Management Sciences*, 2 (6), 2226-3624.
- Folorunso, O.O. Adewale, A.J. and Abodunde, S.M. (2014). Exploring the Effect of Organizational Commitment Dimensions on Employees Performance: An Empirical

- Evidence from Academic Staff of Oyo State Owned Tertiary Institutions, Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 4, (8). 275-286.
- Gabris, G. T. & Simo, G. (1995) Public Sector Motivation as an Independent Variable Affecting Career Decisions, *Public Personnel Management*, 24 (1) 33-51
- Gbadamosi, G. (2003). HRM and the commitment rhetoric: Challenges for Africa. *Management Decision*, 41(3), 274-280.
- Gberevbie, D. E. (2017). *Public administration: A conceptual perspective*. Ibadan, Nigeria: Cardinal Publishers.
- Gberevbie, D., Joshua, S., Excellence-Oluye, N., Oyeyemi, A. (2017). Accountability for sustainable development and the challenges of leadership in Nigeria, 1999-2015. *Sage Open*, 7(4).
- George, J.M. & Jones, G.R. (1999). *Understanding and Managing Organizational Behavior*. Addison-Wesley, Business & Economics.
- Goulet, L. R. & Frank M.L. (2002) Organizational Commitment across Three Sectors: Public, Non-Profit, and For-Profit. *Public Personnel Management* 31(2)
- Gunlu, E., & Aksarayli, M. (2010). Job satisfaction and organizational commitment of Hotel Managers in Turkey. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 22
- Hackman, J. R., & Oldham, G. R. (1976). Motivation through the design of work: Test of a theory. *Organizational Behavior & Human Performance*, 16(2), 250-279.
- Jain, P., and Duggal, T. (2015). The role of transformational leadership in organisational commitment. *International Journal of Business Quantitative Economics and Applied Management Research*, 1(5), 1-11.
- Jurkiewicz, C. L., Massey, Jr., T. K. & Brown, R.G. (1998) Motivation in Public and Private Organizations: A Comparative Study. *Public Productivity & Management Review* 21, (3) 230-250.
- Jaskyte, K. (2004). Assessing changes in employees' perceptions of leadership behavior, job design, and organizational arrangements and their job satisfaction and commitment. *Journal of Human Service Management*, 27 (4), 73-98.
- Khan, H. Razi, A., Ali, S.A, and Asghar A. (2011). A study on relationship between organizational job commitment, and its determinants among CSRs and managerial level employees of Pakistan (Telecommunication sector), *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 3, (11), 269-284.
- Kipkebut, D. J. (2010) *Organisational commitment and job satisfaction in higher educational institutions: the Kenyan case*. PhD thesis, Middlesex University.
- Loui, K. (1995). Understanding employee commitment in the public organization: A study of the juvenile detention center. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 18, 1269-1295.
- Mathieu, J.E, & Zajac, D.M. (1990). A review and meta-analysis of the antecedents, correlates, and consequences of organisational commitment. *Psychological Bulletin*, 108, 171-194.
- Meyer, J. P. & Allen, J.N. (1997). *Commitment in the Workplace: Theory, Research, and Application*. SAGE Publications, Inc.
- Meyer, J.P., Allen, T & Smith, C.A. (1993). Commitment to Organizations and Occupations: Extension and Test of a Three-Component Conceptualization *Journal of Applied Psychology* 78 (4) 538-551.
- Mogaji, A.A. (1997). The effect of organizational climate on employee commitment, involvement and motivation from Nigerian manufacturing industry. *Unpublished Ph.D Thesis, University of Lagos, Lagos*.
- Morakinyo, A.R. (2010). Job-related factors, leadership, motivation and career commitment in a Nigeria College of Education. *Pakistan Journal of Business and Economic Review*, 1 (1), 41-58.
- Mottoh, S. N. (2015). The influence of transformational and transactional leadership style on employee performance (Case study: Dinas Kesehatan Manado). *Jurnal Berkala Ilmiah Efisiensi*, 15, 436-446.
- Mowday, R., Steers, R. & Porter, L. (1979). The measurement of organizational commitment. *Journal of Vocational Behaviour*, 14, 224 - 247.

- Njoku, E. C., Ebeh, R. E. &Mbaeri, S.O. (2017) Personality traits as predictors of organizational commitment among public and private sector employees in Enugu, Nigeria, *British Journal of Psychology Research*, 5, (2) 9-23.
- Omolayo, B. and Owolabi, A.B. (2007) Monetary Rewards: A Predictor of Employee's Commitment to Medium Scale Organizations in Nigeria. *Bangladesh e-journal of Sociology*, 4, (1) 42-48.
- Osemeke, M. (2016).Identification of Determinants of Organizational Commitment and Employee Job Satisfaction.*African Research Review* 10(2):81 .
- Parvin, M., &Kabir, N. (2011) Factors affecting employee job satisfaction of pharmaceutical sector. *Australian Journal of Business and Management Research*, 1, 113-123.
- Perry, J. L., & Porter, L. W. (1982). Factors affecting the context for motivation in public organizations. *Academy of Management Review*, 7, 89-98.
- Porter, L. W., Steers, R. M., Mowday, R. T., &Boulian, P. V. (1974). Organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and turnover among psychiatric technicians. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 59(5), 603-609.
- Rajendran, M. &Raduan, C.R. (2005) Antecedents and outcaomes of organizational commitment among Malaysian Engineers, *American Journal of Applied Sciences*, 2 (6), 1095-1100.
- Rose, M. (2001) `Disparate Measures in the Workplace: Quantifying Overall Job Satisfaction' . Colchester: *Institute of Social and Economic Research, 2001 British Household Panel Survey Researchers' Conference*, 5-7 July.
- Salami, S.O. (2008) Demographic and Psychological Factors Predicting Organizational Commitment among Industrial Workers.*Anthropologist*, 10, 31-38.
- Spector, P.E. (1997). *Job satisfaction: applications, assessment, causes and consequences*. London: Sage Publication.
- Tella, A., Ayeni, C.O., &Popoola, S.O. (2007). Work motivation, job satisfaction and organisational commitment of library personnel in academic and research libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1-16.
- Weiss, D.J., Dawis, R. V., England, G.W., &Lofquist, L.H (1967).*Manual for the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire*.Minneapolis in University of Minnesota.